

FIDELIS, European Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories

Position Statement on the EOSC Federation Handbook

October 2025

This document provides a response to the EOSC Federation Handbook Version 1 that was published in March 2025. The FIDELIS Network members welcome the possibility to provide feedback on the Handbook and call for a more structured dialogue to shape clear and achievable guidance for repositories to enter the EOSC Federation of Nodes.

The EOSC Federation Handbook offers an overview of the organisational and operational structure and technical characteristics of the EOSC Federation. It aims to serve as a practical guideline for organisations that are interested in making their resources available within and across the EOSC Federation.

The FIDELIS Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories (TDRs) was recently established and has a membership of over 50 European repositories. The Network aims to support its members in becoming and remaining trustworthy and FAIR-enabling over time, developing common frameworks for repository policies and workflows, and thus helping repositories implement and sustain best practices in data management.

TDRs are a critical pillar of the research ecosystem, ensuring secure and sustained access to digital research objects. They serve as essential infrastructure in the research data lifecycle, enabling researchers to share, access, and reuse data and other digital objects while ensuring the long-term preservation of research outputs.

As EOSC continues to expand, the role of TDRs grows ever more significant. TDRs provide core services that enable the EOSC not only to deliver FAIR data, but also to ensure that they maintain their FAIR characteristics over time.

The EOSC Federation Handbook is a fundamental document for the establishment of the EOSC Federation. It is therefore important both for the EOSC and the repositories that the Handbook provides clear and achievable guidance on what is required from the repositories.

The FIDELIS Network members welcome the possibility to provide feedback on the Handbook. The EU-funded projects FIDELIS and EOSC-EDEN have already given detailed feedback via the survey.

Beyond this feedback, the Network would welcome the opportunity to interact with the EOSC Association to prepare TDRs for participation in the EOSC Federation. The Network membership also offers its knowledge and experience to help shape requirements for repositories to enter the Federation, that are understandable and achievable. The Network believes a more structured dialogue would be mutually beneficial.